

Assessment of Instructional Facilities, Methods and Learning Outcomes in History among Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State

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Abstract

The study tends to examine the Assessment of instructional facilities, methods and learning outcomes in history learning among secondary school students in sokoto. The sample of the study consists of 306(Male 177 and Female 129) SS2 history students. This sample was arrived at by selecting six Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis using purposive sampling technique on the basis of if history is being offered in the schools, co-education and being a government secondary school, Simple random sampling technique was adopted to select students using an intact class. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain data and simple percentages were used to analyze results. The findings of the study revealed that: there is lack of adequate instructional facility. The techniques of instruction are mostly teacher-centered and the teachers - students' ratio is not encouraging for the students' population. The result of learning outcomes revealed that the subject content is mostly difficult for the students to comprehend. The level of interest exhibited by the students is not encouraging for learning history. Provisions for fieldtrips/excursions, experienced and qualified history teachers should be employed for teaching and learning of History in all Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis and beyond.

Key words: Instructional methods, Instructional facility, Learning outcomes, and Students

Introduction

As a study of the past happenings, History draws on significant events of the past to inform the present and to safeguard the future, in effect, History does not study the past in isolation from the present, but relates intricately, the successes, achievements and failures of antecedent generations to the contemporary case and sets the stage for a better living in the morrow (Boadu, 2016). In this light, it is believed that History is a systematic account of the past events in relation to the present time in order to be able to predict the future for the purpose of shaping it for better. The goal of History teaching in schools is to help young people develop an integrated spiritual world, via assimilation of the ethno-cultural, national and universal values that have been developed in the course of historical development, and by giving them experience in defining themselves in relation to these values.

In Nigeria, the history teaching and learning has been changed over the years from time to time when it was a vibrant school subject to the time when it has become excised from the primary and junior secondary school curriculum(Jyothish, 2021). Soon, history became a favorite subject on the school's curriculum at independence in Nigeria. First at the university college, Ibadan and later, the University of Ibadan, began to review the school's curriculum to introduce aspects of Nigeria and African history away from the colonial history that was taught that paid much attention to the ancient world(Baba et al., 2022). History as a subject also feature prominently at the higher school certificate (HSC) program which sought to prepare students for admission to the universities. By1966, the subject was among the most favoured subject at the HSC examinations and in which the candidates excelled. While the principal passes were English 244, Latin 3, Geography 269, Mathematics 88, and French 19, History recorded 414(Unya, 2022), However, the course of the teaching history was to be adversely affected by the events which followed the convening of the 1969 national curriculum conference followed by adaptation of a national policy of education and the subsequent arrival of the 6-3-3-4 system of education "the1969 conference which was expected to bring hope

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to the country's educational system turned out to be the beginning of the decline of history teaching in schools. In the end, the curriculum reform which grew from that conference led to the reduction of the status of history (Rakhbar, 2021).

Statement of the Research Problem

In Nigeria, the teaching and learning of History in schools is undergoing tremendous changing in terms of modernization, methodologies which can be understood only in the context of the subject. It is now clear that the process of History teaching and learning has become more varied and interesting, with a possibility for greater personal input. At the same time, it should be remembered that History education is based on a rich legacy. Further stated that, History teaching and learning in Nigerian schools has a long tradition, the indisputable achievement of the History as a subject and the methodologies used in teaching it have been recognized internationally. However, it should be noted that teaching and learning of History in schools has witnessed some changes over the years (Diso & Haruna, 2020). The changes have really affected the structure of History education, the principles for selecting subject matter and the instructional materials used to teach the subject. Baba *et al.* (2022), stated that recommended methods were not used by History teachers in teaching the subject, and even those used were not used appropriately. It was also revealed that instructional resources were not frequently used in History lessons because such resources were either not available at all or were inadequate. Also, Students were also found to possess negative perceptions about the subject as they regarded History as a compendium of facts to be memorized.

An effective History teacher does not rely on a single method of teaching (Diso & Haruna, 2020). Effectiveness is multi-dimensional rather than non dimensional. And that effective teaching of History involves setting conditions that make selected works more interesting (Jyothish, 2021). Effective instruction has a bearing on the interest of students and their motivation to learning History; and also influences them to make critical judgment on historical issues, and understand current events in the appropriate historical context (Alison and Alison, 2021). Rahbar (2021) observed that ambitious teachers have a good depth of understanding regarding their subject matter and consciously seek ways of connecting the subject matter to students' experiences. Effective History teaching thus, involves teaching in no single pattern, taking no single shape in teaching, and assessing students in no single fashion. Consequently, History as a subject which is being taught in senior secondary schools is facing a lot of challenges in terms of teaching facility, methods of instruction and students activity in response to the instructional process. The present study sought to investigate the effect of instructional facility, methods of instruction and learning outcomes in the teaching of History in Secondary Schools within Sokoto.

Research Questions

1. What is the current status of instructional facility for teaching of History as a subject in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis?
2. What instructional Techniques are being employed in the teaching of History in Senior Secondary schools in Sokoto Metropolis?
3. What type of learning outcomes were obtained in the teaching and learning of history among secondary school students in Sokoto Metropolis

Research Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design according to Ali 2010a. The survey design seeks to document and describe what, present status of existence or absence of what is under investigation. The research population of this study comprises of 1842 (Male 1062 & Females 780) senior secondary school students from six schools.

The sample size of this study is 306 senior secondary school students drawn from the study population of 1842. The research employed the stratification proportionate random sample technique. The bases considered for the selection were sex and socio economic status.

Instrumentation

Structured interview and on-the-spot observation were administered to collate the responses from the respondents on the different aspects of the research study. The information solicited includes responses on students' data such as age, gender, occupation of the parents, school and class of the students. Data regarding the subject of study (Teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools) in Sokoto Metropolis focuses on a variety of considerations. These range from instructional

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procedures/techniques, through availability of training facility to acquired skills, experiences and perceptions of the students on the subject matter and the instructional processes.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the current status of instructional facility for teaching of History subject in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis?

Table 1: Percentage of respondents showing the status of instructional facility for teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto

S/N	Instructional Facility	Sample (N)	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
1	Text Books available	306	113	36.93	4 th
2	Library up-to-date	306	122	39.87	3 rd
3	Use of teaching aids	306	171	55.88	2 nd
4	Field Trips	306	66	21.57	5 th
5	Make improvisation	306	271	88.56	1 st

Table 1 shows the percentage responses in terms of instructional facility for the teaching of History. The result indicates a higher percentage of improvisation (88.56%) over other requirements. This is followed by the use of teaching aids in History classes (55.88). Library standard had 39.87%, text books had 36.93%, and the least, fieldtrips had 21.57%.

Research Question 2

What were the percentage responses regarding the style/techniques for the teaching of History in the Senior Secondary Schools within Sokoto?

Table 2: Percentage of respondents showing style/techniques of teaching History in the Senior Secondary Schools within Sokoto

S/N	Method/style of instruction	Sample N.	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
1	Student centered	306	102	33.33	4 th
2	Teachers availability	306	93	30.39	5 th
3	Regular Teaching	306	226	73.85	2 nd
4	Give and mark assignments	306	130	42.48	3 rd
5	Ask & answer students questions	306	254	83.00	1 st

Table 2 shows percentage of positive responses in terms of style/techniques for the teaching History. The style of asking and answering students' questions by the teacher had the highest response of 83.00% followed by regular teaching with 73.85%. Administering and marking of students' assignments ranks 3rd with 42.48%. Student centered teaching and availability of teachers for History had the lowest responses of 33.33% and 30.39% respectively.

Research Question 3

What were the percentage responses regarding learning outcomes/acquired skills from the teaching of History in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto?

Table 3: Percentage of respondents showing learning outcomes/acquired skills from the lessons of History classes in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto

Sample (N).	S/N	Learning outcome/ Students response	No. of Respondents agreed	% of Respondents agreed	Rank of Sources
306	1	Class interesting	256	83.66	3 rd

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306	2	Content difficult to understand	199	65.03	4 th
306	3	School management show interest	151	49.34	5 th
306	4	Teacher tolerant	258	84.31	2 nd
306	5	Delivers content appropriately	266	86.92	1 st

Table 3 shows percentage of respondents indicating learning outcomes from the teaching of History. Appropriate delivery of lesson have the highest response (86.92%) closely followed by the teachers' tolerance (84.31%) and students' interest in the lessons delivery (83.66%). Difficulty in understanding the subject however received 65.03% positive response and interest in the subject by the school management received 49.34% positive response.

Discussion

Availability and effective utilization of instructional facility is of paramount importance in the teaching and learning of any subject no matter how complex. The findings of this study revealed high level of improvisation of instructional materials for teaching of History with 88.56% report of improvisation by the teachers. This is a clear indication of lack or shortage of standard facility for teaching the subject. According to Rahbar (2021), modern methods and techniques of teaching History in school education system along with good teaching aids are vital requirements for effective curriculum implementation. The response on the availability of teaching aids merely indicates the use of maps, which are inadequate for contemporary teaching of the subject. With the report of low standard of library facility for history, presence of mostly outdated textbooks and lack of regular fieldtrips on the subject, the challenges for teaching of history seem enormous. Alison and Alison (2021) highlighted on the instrumental role of both instructional materials and information communication technology in the teaching and learning of History. Although students are allowed to ask questions and get answers from the history teachers, student centered teaching and availability of teachers for the subject had the lowest responses of 33.33% and 30.39% respectively. The research findings revealed that there are no enough history teachers. This trend leads to the teaching of History by other subjects' teachers without requisite training and skills in the area. In addition to the aforementioned, many history teachers capitalize on teacher-centered approach which limits students' capabilities. Because the students use to be passive with little or none participation, this eventually led to the shortage of students in the field of history.

On the use of instructional materials, the high negative response from the study points out the implications of possible wrong perception and poor understanding of history subject by the students. With regards to the excursion and field trip, the high negative response from the study means that, students are not visiting valuable historical sites which will arouse the interest of the students, which is also important in the retention of knowledge. Consequently, the students perceive history as just mere story and irrelevant to the modern time.

Result shows high percentage of respondents for appropriate lessons delivery and teacher tolerance in History lessons. Respondents however reported much difficulty in understanding History lessons and low interest by the school managements in the teaching of the subject.

Majority of respondents (83.0%) agreed that History teachers allow students to ask questions and also ask the students questions related to the subject matter being discussed. Although this is essential in improving the process of instruction in the subject, the student-centered instructional style by most teachers of the subject (33.33%) and unavailability of teachers of History in the schools (30.39%), is impacting negatively on the general performance of the students and the prospect of the course in general. In addition the lack of interest in teaching the subject on the side of school management was highly reported by the respondents. This indicates that the school managements pay little or no attention in the teaching of History as a subject in the senior secondary schools.

On the availability of history textbooks, mostly poor and outdated books have been reported by the respondents. This led to the problem of wrong perception and poor understanding of history by the students. With regards to the excursion and field trip, poor response means that, students are not visiting valuable historical sites which will arouse the interest of the students and it also aid the retention of knowledge. Consequently, the students perceive history as just mere story and irrelevant to the modern time. Concerning interest the interest by the school management about the teaching of History, This indicates that school management has little or no interest in history as a subject. It is apparent therefore, that, there is need for the adjustment of teaching method from teacher-centered to students-oriented, for the students to participate more. School management or the authority provide the available and modem history textbooks, then to provide fertile ground for the excursion and field trip to take place. Also, there is a need for the provision of the adequate and appropriate instructional materials.

Conclusion

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The study revealed that, there is an acute shortage of qualified history teachers with sufficient teaching experience. It has also been found that, history teachers are overworked as they teach a large number of classes and other subjects apart from history. This affects their performance in the teaching of history. Poor interest of students and the schools management in the subject have been reported. This is probably because of inability of the authorities to provide the appropriate history textbooks relevant to the history as a subject. This problem is of course related to the problems of ill-equipped libraries discovered during the research.

Another problem militating against effective history teaching and learning is that of instructional materials. Teachers in the schools surveyed mainly use maps neglecting the use of a variety of instructional materials such as pictures, charts. The teachers fail to use their expertise knowledge to make history teaching more interesting. This led to the assumption and belief by the students that history is mere stories and irrelevant facts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should include History as a core subject in the curriculum and make it compulsory for all students in secondary schools like other subjects such as Mathematics and English Language.
2. History should be made more interesting through well-trained History teachers who can teach the subject and make it interesting to the students.
3. There is need for consistence in Government policies that will cater for students needs in History as a subject in Nigerian secondary schools.
4. History teachers should not be overburdened with teaching of other subjects. They should be allowed to concentrate on history as their teaching subject.
5. The use of instructional materials is a very important, motivator as it arouses and sustains students' interest. The history teacher should use a variety of instructional materials and not just maps. Audio, audio-visual, pictures and charts as well as physical objects should serve as instructional materials for the teaching of History.

Acknowledgement

The authors hereby wish to acknowledge the tremendous support received from the TETFUND for sponsoring the IBR (institution based research, which led to this paper publication. The assistance both administrative and technical by the management and colleagues at the FCE Gidan Madi, Sokoto State is highly appreciated by the authors.

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